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Impact of Blanching Pretreatment on the Quality Characteristics of Three Varieties of Oven Dried Eggplant

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Abstract

Eggplant possesses appreciable reserve of nutrients and loads of phytochemical compounds. Processing will help minimize the wastage and increase consumption. In this study, three cultivars of eggplant were pre-treated, oven-dried and ground into coarse powders with the intent of retaining the nutrients. The functional properties, proximate, vitamin, mineral, phytochemical and anti-nutrient composition as well as the sensory characteristics were determined. The results showed that the eggplant powders had high water absorption capacity (6.90 - 11.50 ml/g), oil absorption capacity (11.20 - 11.70 ml/g), emulsion capacity (25.02 - 35.40 %) and wettability (11.00 - 15.50 sec). However, pre-treatment was found to reduce the functional properties of the eggplant powders compared to the control samples. The level of moisture (5.40 - 6.15 %) and ash (7.50 - 8.00 %) content was increased by blanching pre-treatment with concurrent reduction in fat (1.85 - 1.45 %), crude fibre (12.75 - 11.93 %) and protein (13.05 - 11.35 %) content. The mineral content was found to be higher in the blanched samples with potassium being the major mineral. Blanching pre-treatment resulted in reducing vitamin content in the samples. The studied eggplant varieties are poor sources of thiamin (0.02 - 0.22 mg/100g), riboflavin (0.02 - 0.17 mg/100g) and tocopherol (0.16 - 0.46 mg/100g), but contained high retinol content (17.89 - 56.11 mg/100g) and significant amount of vitamin C (1.05 - 6.00 mg/100g). Similarly, pretreatment resulted in reduced phytochemical and antinutritional properties in the eggplant powders. Organoleptically, the eggplant powders had better appearance with no change in taste, but reduced preference in terms of texture, flavour and general acceptability. The eggplant powders can be utilized as functional ingredient for food enrichment.

Keywords: Eggplant, phytochemicals, anti-nutrients, functional properties, sensory.

Introduction

Eggplant (*Solanum Melongena L.*), is an integral part of the African tradition and diet. It is consumed almost on a daily basis in both rural and urban families. There is a wide range of varieties which is evident in their different colours such as violet, cream, orange, pink, red, plum, burgundy, yellow, white, green, lime, lavender, purple or dusky black, striped and multi-coloured. More so, besides the well-known conventional egg-shaped *Solanum*, there are also round, flat, ribbed, and pumpkin-like in shape (McGuire, 2013). They possess various nutritional and pharmacological properties that make them valuable addition to diets. This is because they have appreciable reserve of nutrients and loads of phytochemical substances, such as anthocyanin, fiber, phenols, ascorbic acid, glycoalkaloids and α -chaconine (Sanchez-Mata *et al.*, 2010), that makes them valuable addition to diets. Anthocyanin, the main phenolic content in eggplant peel is responsible for the pigmentation (Ossamulu *et al.*, 2014; Horbowicz *et al.*, 2018). The bitter taste of eggplant has been attributed to polyphenols (Mazza *et al.*, 2004). The eggplant is ranked among the top 10 vegetables in terms of oxygen radical absorbance capacity (Okwu and Josiah, 2006).

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Thus, eggplant has the capacity to serve as a medicinal plant in maintaining a healthy gut, cure ailments and prevent diseases (Lakshman, 2012). There is an indication from previous studies that a correlation exists between the increasing consumption of eggplant and a reduction in the risk of overall mortality, overweight, high blood glucose level and cardiovascular conditions (Ossei *et al.*, 2012). Currently eggplants are utilized in the preparation of garden egg stews, soups, and sauces, or as dessert when consumed in its raw form (Agoreyo *et al.*, 2012). They can also be fried or grilled and is sometimes used as a meat substitute in vegetarian cuisines due to its texture and bulk (Akiyama *et al.*, 2001).

Despite their healthy roles, very little research has been carried out to effectively preserve and package the product. Previous studies have focused on the nutritional, polyphenolic and antioxidant capacity of raw eggplant. A large proportion of this commodity is reportedly wasted, especially during the harvest season, which is usually accompanied by glut (Agoreyo *et al.*, 2012). This study aimed at finding alternative ways of processing eggplant into the functional ingredient, which will increase the utilization in the preparation of healthy cuisine and food products. The effect of steam blanching pre-treatments on the quality characteristics of three varieties of oven-dried eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) was investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Source of raw material

The three varieties of eggplant, *Solanum macrocarpon*, *Solanum aethiopicum* and *Solanum gilo* (Plates 1, 2 and 3) used for this study were purchased at Akpan Andem market in Uyo, Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria.

Plate 1: *Solanum macrocarpon*. Plate 2: *Solanum aethiopicum*. Plate 3: *Solanum gilo*.

Sample preparation

The three eggplant varieties were sorted and washed to remove dirt. They were cut to uniform smaller sizes to expose the maximum surface area. The cut eggplants varieties were divided into 2 lots. The first lots were steam blanched at 80 °C for 30 sec, cooled to room temperature, salted and oven-dried at 60°C until constant weight was achieved, and were labeled SMB (*Solanum macrocarpon*), SAB (*Solanum aethiopicum*) and SGB (*Solanum gilo*) (Table1). The second lots of the 3 varieties were subjected to the same process but without steam blanching (SMC, SAC, and SGC). The dried samples were hammer milled and sieved with 0.42 mm pore size to obtain their respective eggplant powders. The samples were then packaged with cellophane and stored at ambient temperature (25-28 °C) prior to analysis.

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Table 1: Sample codes representing each eggplant powder.

Sample	Sample Codes
<i>S. macrocarpon</i> (unblanched)	SMC
<i>S. aethiopicum</i> (unblanched)	SAC
<i>S. gilo</i> (unblanched)	SGC
<i>S. macrocarpon</i> (Steam blanched)	SMB
<i>S. aethiopicum</i> sample (Steam blanched)	SAB
<i>S. gilo</i> (Steam blanched)	SGB

METHODS OF ANALYSES

Functional analysis

Determination of viscosity, gelation capacity, bulk density, wettability, and water/oil absorption capacity, emulsion capacity and swelling index of the samples were determined using the method described by Onwuka (2010).

Proximate analysis

The method recommended by Association of Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2000) was used for the determination of moisture, ash, crude fat, crude fibre and crude protein content of the samples, while the carbohydrate content of the samples was determined by difference as described by Onwuka (2018).

Mineral analysis

The potassium, magnesium, calcium, sodium, phosphorous, and Iron content of the samples were determined according to the method described by AOAC (2000).

Vitamin analysis

Determination of vitamin B₁, (thiamine), vitamin B₂ (riboflavin) vitamin B₃, vitamin C, and vitamin E, contents of the samples were determined using Spectrophotometric method as described by Rukowski (2010).

Phytochemical analysis

The method described by Eze and Kanu (2015) was used in the determination of alkaloids and phenols, while flavonoids and sterols were determined according to the method described by Osagie (2011).

Anti-nutrients analysis

The determination of tannin and oxalate were carried out using the method described by Osagie (2011). Saponin was determined according to the method described by Eze and Kanu (2015). The method described by Okwu (2005) was used in determining cyanogenic glucosides and phytate.

Sensory analysis

Sensory evaluation of the samples was carried out using the method described by Iwe (2010). The sensory attributes of the garden egg powders which include taste, flavour, colour, texture and overall acceptability were

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evaluated using a 9-point hedonic scale with 1 representing the least score (dislike extremely), 5 as neither like nor dislike and 9 the highest score (like extremely).

Statistical analysis

The statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) software version 18.0 was used. The results were evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and were presented as the mean value \pm SD (standard deviation of the mean) for the samples. Differences among the means were assessed using the Duncan's Multiple Range Test to determine which mean values were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Functional Properties

The functional properties of both unblanched and steam-blanched *Solanum aethiopicum*, *S. macrocarpon*, and *S. gilo* eggplants are presented in Table 2. The water absorption capacity (WAC) of the blanched eggplant powders ranged from 6.90 to 10.00 g/ml, while those of the control samples ranged from 10.00 to 11.50 g/ml. These results are higher than the value (1.8 g/ml) reported by Rodriguez-Jimenez *et al.* (2018). This could be attributed to the level of drying achieved in both studies since drying increases the absorption capacity of flour (Hayata *et al.*, 2006). Niba *et al.* (2001) stated that WAC is important in bulking and could be useful in bakery products. The oil absorption capacity (OAC) of SAB (11.20 ml/g) was lower than other samples (11.30 – 11.70 ml/g). However, the OAC values for all the samples were high. High oil absorption capacity exhibited by all the samples will enhance the retention of flavor, increase the mouth feel of products and would make the eggplant powders valuable in ground meat formulations, meat replacers and in soups (Onimawo and Egbekun, 1998). The bulk density (BD) of the samples ranged between 0.48 - 0.53 g/ml. The control samples (0.48 - 0.51 g/ml) had lower BD compared to the blanched samples (0.51 - 0.53 g/ml). This range corresponds with the value (0.56 g/ml) reported for African breadfruit pulp flour by Adepeju *et al.* (2011).

Table 2: Functional properties of eggplants powders.

Sample codes	Water Absorption Capacity (ml/g)	Oil Absorption Capacity (ml/g)	Bulk density (g/ml)	Emulsion capacity (%)	Foam capacity (%)	Swelling index
SMC	11.50 ^a \pm 0.35	11.70 ^a \pm 0.14	0.51 ^c \pm 0.00	32.07 ^b \pm 0.56	9.45 ^b \pm 0.00	3.92 ^a \pm 0.00
SAC	10.75 ^b \pm 0.14	11.50 ^{bc} \pm 0.00	0.50 ^d \pm 0.00	35.40 ^a \pm 0.00	11.33 ^a \pm 0.18	3.40 ^b \pm 0.05
SGC	10.00 ^c \pm 0.00	11.60 ^b \pm 0.00	0.48 ^e \pm 0.00	28.62 ^d \pm 0.00	8.80 ^c \pm 0.17	2.86 ^c \pm 0.00
SMB	7.00 ^d \pm 0.00	11.40 ^{cd} \pm 0.00	0.53 ^a \pm 0.00	27.78 ^d \pm 0.46	7.28 ^d \pm 0.00	1.83 ^d \pm 0.05
SAB	10.00 ^c \pm 0.00	11.20 ^e \pm 0.00	0.52 ^b \pm 0.00	30.73 ^c \pm 0.39	8.53 ^c \pm 0.18	1.74 ^d \pm 0.08
SGB	6.90 ^d \pm 0.14	11.30 ^{de} \pm 0.00	0.51 ^c \pm 0.00	25.02 ^e \pm 0.90	6.52 ^e \pm 0.00	1.47 ^e \pm 0.00

The data are the mean value \pm standard deviation (SD) of triplicate samples. Figures with different superscripts in the column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The low BD exhibited by the samples would be advantageous when used in food formulation-mix (Amandikwa, 2012). The emulsion capacity of the samples ranged from 25.02 to 35.40%. Pre-treatment

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significantly decreased the emulsion capacity of the eggplant powder samples, such that, the steam blanched samples had lower emulsion capacity (27.78 - 30.73 %) than the control samples (28.63 - 35.40 %). This shows a desirable emulsifying ability. The foam capacity (FC) of the samples varied from 6.52 to 11.33 %. The foam capacity is an index of foamability of protein dispersion. Foams improve texture, and it is affected by processing methods (Onimawo and Akubor, 2005). This is evidently seen in the present study such that the FC values of the control samples (8.80 - 9.45 %) are higher than the pre-treated samples (6.52 - 8.53 %). This inferred that heat treatment, such as steam blanching, might affect the foaming capacity of eggplant flours/powders when used in food formulations. The swelling index of the samples varied from 1.47 to 3.92. The control samples had higher swelling index (2.86 - 3.92) than the steam blanched samples (1.47 - 1.83), which suggested that blanching might have affected the eggplant starch granules. Generally, eggplant samples showed good swelling index when compared to crops like cassava. This is because of the type of granules eggplant starch has and its highly digestible nature (Ojinaka *et al.*, 2009).

Proximate composition

The results of the proximate analysis are presented in Table 3. The moisture content values (5.40 - 6.15 %) obtained in this study compared favourably with the values reported by Eze and Kanu (2015) and Rodriguez-Jimenez *et al.* (2018) but lower than the value reported by Edem *et al.* (2009). The control samples (5.40 - 5.80 %) had lower moisture values compared to the pretreated samples (5.7 - 6.15 %). This could be associated with the possible increase in water absorption during pre-treatment (steam blanching). Since moisture content can be used as an index of stability of foods (Offor, 2015), it could be presumed that the blanched samples would have lower shelf stability. The protein content was higher in the control samples (12.05 - 13.05 %) than in the blanched samples (11.35 - 12.25 %) of all the varieties. This could be attributed to the impact of denaturation from heating on the blanched samples. The result obtained in this study was lower than 12.00 - 15.00 % reported by Uthumporn *et al.* (2016). Thus, eggplant could be used to supplement some low protein staple foods. The fat content of the samples ranged from 1.45 to 1.85 %. The pre-treated samples of *S. macrocarpon* (SMB) and *S. aethiopicum* (SAB) had higher fat content than their corresponding unblanched samples. No significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was recorded in the fat content of both the pretreated (SGB) and the control sample (SGC) of *S. gilo* (1.45 %). The low-fat content of the eggplant powders would be beneficial during storage. The crude fibre content of the samples was high (11.93 - 12.75 %). Crude fiber refers to the indigestible plant material. The crude fibre content of the control and pre-treated samples were not significantly different ($p > 0.05$), which suggested that pre-treatment of eggplant had minimal impact on their fibre content. However, the result obtained in this study is higher than the value (2.92 %) reported by Chinedu *et al.* (2011). The high crude fibre content obtained in this study implied that the samples would be beneficial in high fibre diets. The pre-treatments operation improved the ash content of the eggplant powders, such that, the blanched samples had higher values (7.60 - 8.00%) than the control samples (7.50 - 7.85%). Since ash content translates to the mineral content of foods (Ndife *et al.*, 2014). It could be inferred that the blanching process would increase the mineral composition of the eggplant powders (Onwuka, 2014).

Table 3: Proximate composition of eggplant powders (%).

Sample codes	Moisture	protein	fat	Crude fibre	Ash	Carbohydrate
SMC	5.50 ^{bc} ± 0.14	12.63 ^b ± 0.18	1.73 ^{ab} ± 0.11	12.20 ^c ± 0.00	7.60 ^c ± 0.14	60.00 ^{bc} ± 0.85
SAC	5.40 ^c ± 0.00	13.05 ^a ± 0.00	1.60 ^{bc} ± 0.00	12.60 ^{ab} ± 0.14	7.85 ^{ab} ± 0.07	59.50 ^c ± 0.07
SGC	5.80 ^b ± 0.14	12.05 ^c ± 0.00	1.45 ^c ± 0.07	11.93 ^d ± 0.11	7.50 ^c ± 0.14	61.23 ^a ± 0.03
SMSB	5.80 ^b ± 0.14	11.80 ^d ± 0.00	1.85 ^a ± 0.07	12.40 ^{bc} ± 0.00	7.70 ^{bc} ± 0.00	60.45 ^{abc} ± 0.21
SASB	5.70 ^{bc} ± 0.14	12.25 ^c ± 0.00	1.75 ^{ab} ± 0.00	12.75 ^a ± 0.07	8.00 ^a ± 0.00	59.55 ^c ± 0.07
SGSB	6.15 ^a ± 0.07	11.35 ^e ± 0.14	1.45 ^c ± 0.07	12.33 ^c ± 0.11	7.60 ^c ± 0.00	60.95 ^{ab} ± 0.28

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The data are the mean value \pm standard deviation (SD) of triplicate samples. Figures with different superscripts in the column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The result obtained in this study compared favourably with the values reported by Rodriguez-Jimenez *et al.* (2018) but higher than that the values reported by Nino-Medina *et al.* (2014). Carbohydrate contents were lowest in control (SAC) (59.50 %) and in pretreated (SAB) (59.55 %) samples of the *S. aethiopicum* variety but highest in control (SGC) (61.23 %) and pre-treated samples (SGB) (60.95 %) of the *S. gilo* variety. There was no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in carbohydrate content of both pretreated and the control samples of *S. aethiopicum* and *S. macrocarpon*. The carbohydrate content obtained in this study is higher than the value (13.03 %) reported by Eze and Kanu (2015). The high carbohydrate content indicated that garden egg is a good source of energy.

Mineral composition

The results of the mineral analysis of the eggplant powders are shown in Table 4. The mineral contents were higher in the blanched samples than in the control samples in all the varieties. Sodium was observed to be lower than potassium in all the studied varieties. The potassium content of the eggplant powders ranged from 718 – 811 mg/100g while that of sodium varied from 328 – 431 mg/100g. Low sodium diet has been reported to be beneficial in the prevention of high blood pressure (Onwuka, 2018). This result corresponds with the findings of (Ossamulu *et al.*, 2014). The high potassium content obtained in all the varieties suggested that the incorporation of the eggplant powders into diet would have a protective effect against excessive sodium intake, and thus, would be beneficial in the prevention of high blood pressure (Helena, 2008). Magnesium which plays a vital role in the activity of many enzymes varied from 30.30 to 40.60 mg/100g in the eggplant powders. These values are lower than the values reported by Usunobun and Okolie (2015) for *Vernonia amygdalina* (681.36 mg/100g) and *Annona muricata* (961.9 mg/100g). Magnesium is beneficial in formation of bone and teeth (Hasslam, 2008). The calcium content of the blanched samples ranged from 22.09 to 33.46 mg/100g whereas those of the unblanched samples ranged from 21.46 to 31.86 mg/100g. These values are higher than the values reported by Eze and Kanu (2015). Calcium is also required for bone development (Helena, 2008). Phosphorous is an important component of energy intermediates (Vance *et al.*, 2003). The phosphorous content ranged from 94.40 to 129.74 mg/100g in the eggplant powders. *S. gilo* variety had the highest value in both the untreated (107.05 mg/100g) and pretreated samples (129.74 mg/100g) compared to other varieties. Iron was higher in both the pre-treated (27.18 mg/100g) and untreated (25.76 mg/100g) samples of *S. macrocarpon* than in the other studied varieties. Iron is required for haemoglobin production (Helena, 2008). NAFDAC requires that food should contain up to 20 - 30 mg/g of calcium, potassium, magnesium, sodium, and phosphorous (NAFDAC, 2012). The mineral content of the eggplant powders exceeded these amounts, indicating that the studied eggplant species are very good sources of minerals.

Vitamin composition

The vitamin content of the eggplant samples was reduced by blanching such that, all the blanched samples had lower vitamin content than the control samples (Table 5). The reduction could be related to the heat sensitivity of vitamins. The retinol content of the blanched samples ranged from (17.89 - 21.58 mg/100g) while that of the control ranged from (52.85 - 56.11 mg/100g). Since the retinol content in the eggplant samples after blanching was high, the eggplant powders could be used for food enrichment.

Table 4: Mineral content of eggplants powders (mg/100g).

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Sample codes	Potassium	Magnesium	Calcium	Sodium	Phosphorous	Iron
SMC	718.75 ^d ±1.08	30.30 ^c ±1.10	21.46 ^e ±0.00	328.13 ^d ±0.66	107.05 ^c ±0.82	25.76 ^b ±0.61
SAC	764.65 ^f ±0.81	34.63 ^b ±0.00	25.90 ^d ±0.68	379.53 ^c ±0.00	94.40 ^c ±1.16	12.65 ^d ±0.00
SGC	807.38 ^b ±1.34	39.11 ^a ±0.74	31.86 ^b ±0.33	427.61 ^b ±1.39	127.52 ^b ±0.47	15.81 ^c ±0.00
SMB	723.08 ^c ±1.39	31.75 ^c ±0.47	22.09 ^e ±0.00	329.68 ^d ±0.00	108.45 ^c ±0.06	27.18 ^a ±0.49
SAB	770.40 ^e ±0.00	36.03 ^b ±0.43	27.08 ^c ±0.49	381.10 ^c ±0.58	97.25 ^d ±0.28	13.45 ^d ±0.37
SGB	811.81 ^a ±0.45	40.60 ^a ±0.60	33.46 ^a ±0.00	431.14 ^a ±1.49	129.74 ^a ±0.46	16.48 ^c ±0.00

The data are the mean value ± standard deviation of triplicate samples. Values with different superscripts in the column are significantly different (p<0.05).

Table 5: Vitamin content of eggplants powders (mg/100g).

Sample codes	Retinol	Thiamine	Riboflavin	Niacin	Ascorbic acid	Tocopherol
SMC	52.85 ^e ±0.64	0.22 ^a ±0.26	0.17 ^a ±0.19	1.11 ^a ±0.12	6.00 ^a ±0.28	0.30 ^b ±0.03
SAC	56.11 ^a ±0.40	0.05 ^a ±0.00	0.04 ^a ±0.00	1.14 ^a ±0.00	5.35 ^b ±0.07	0.41 ^a ±0.03
SGC	54.71 ^b ±0.47	0.05 ^a ±0.00	0.04 ^a ±0.00	1.21 ^a ±0.00	4.69 ^c ±0.38	0.46 ^a ±0.09
SMB	17.89 ^f ±0.62	0.02 ^a ±0.00	0.02 ^a ±0.01	0.51 ^c ±0.04	1.36 ^d ±0.09	0.16 ^c ±0.02
SAB	21.58 ^d ±0.00	0.03 ^a ±0.01	0.02 ^a ±0.00	0.55 ^{bc} ±0.04	1.17 ^d ±0.00	0.19 ^{bc} ±0.01
SGB	20.04 ^e ±0.55	0.03 ^a ±0.00	0.02 ^a ±0.00	0.65 ^b ±0.03	1.05 ^d ±0.04	0.25 ^{bc} ±0.03

The data are mean value ± standard deviation of triplicate samples. Values with different superscripts in the column are significantly different (p<0.05).

Retinol is important for improved vision and maintenance of epithelial cell functions (Akuyili *et al.*, 2013). The thiamine content of the eggplant powders was generally lower (0.02 - 0.22 mg/100g). Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin) plays a supportive role in the treatment of sickle-cell anaemia (Knapp, 2011). The values obtained in this study are low for both blanched (0.02 mg/100g) and unblanched samples (0.04 - 0.17 mg/100g) for all the varieties. These values were low compared to 10.71 mg/100g reported by (Eze and Kanu, 2015). Thus, the eggplant powders are poor in riboflavin. The Niacin (Vitamin B3) contents of unblanched eggplant samples were higher (1.11 - 1.14 mg/100g) than in the blanched samples (0.51 - 0.65 mg/100g). These values are low compared to (8.50 mg) reported by Osei *et al.* (2012) and 7.33 mg reported by Eze and Kanu (2015) for *S. gilo*. Vitamin B3 is a precursor for enzyme co-factors that assist in their work as catalyst in body metabolism. Its deficiency causes pellagra (Duel and Sturtz, 2010). Vitamin C is a very important antioxidant, required for proper development and health of man (Knapp, 2011). *S. macrocarpon* was found to contain higher vitamin C content than other studied varieties. However, the results (1.05 - 6.00 mg/100g) obtained in this study corresponds to the value (2.40 mg/100g) reported by (Offor and Igwe, 2015) for *S. gilo*. Tocopherol which is an important antioxidant was low (0.16 - 0.46 mg/100g) in all the studied eggplant varieties, indicating that they are not rich sources of tocopherol.

Phytochemical properties

Phytochemical analysis of the eggplant powders revealed that there were significant differences (P>0.05) in the parameters evaluated (Table 6). The level of flavonoid in the samples ranged from 0.14 - 0.75 µg/100g.

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Ossamulu *et al.* (2014) reported that flavonoid concentration ranged between 16.88 - 12.53 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ for *S. gilo*, *S. aethiopicum*, and *S. macrocarpon*. The flavonoid content of the control samples (0.40 - 0.75 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) was higher than those of the pretreated samples (0.14 - 0.30 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$). Thus, blanching reduced the flavonoid concentration in the samples. The flavonoid (nasunin) isolated from the peel of eggplant fruits has demonstrated to be potent free radical scavenger (Noda *et al.*, 2000). Similar to flavonoids, the alkaloids content of pretreated samples was low (0.02 - 0.06 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) compared to those of the control samples (0.08-0.23 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$). Blanching reduced the alkaloid content of the eggplant powders. Blanching was found to reduce the total polyphenol content of the eggplants (0.22 - 0.57 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) compared to unblanched samples (0.70 - 0.57 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$). This could be attributed to the heat sensitivity of the polyphenols due to degradation (Huang *et al.*, 2004). Consequently, reducing their potential health benefits (Osei *et al.*, 2012). Phenolics have reported being involved in various physiological functions, which include antioxidant, antitumor and antimutagenic activities (Offor, 2015). The carotenoid content of the eggplant powders decreased with processing. The unblanched varieties had higher carotenoid content (0.18 - 0.34 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) than the blanched samples (0.07 - 0.15 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$). This could be attributed to the fact that carotenoid retention decreases with longer processing time and cutting or pureeing of the food (Rodriguez-Amaya and Kimura, 2004). Similar to other phytochemicals analyzed in this study, the level of sterols in the control samples (1.40 - 1.92 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$) was higher compared with the level in the pre-treated samples (0.78 - 1.26 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$). The blanched samples had lower phytochemical contents in the three varieties studied. Consequently, blanching negatively affected the medicinal components of the eggplants.

Table 6: Phytochemical properties of eggplant powders ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$).

Sample codes	Flavonoids	Alkaloids	Phenols	Steroids	Carotenoids
SMC	0.75 ^a ± 0.00	0.23 ^a ± 0.04	1.52 ^a ± 0.00	1.40 ^b ± 0.32	0.31 ^a ± 0.01
SAC	0.54 ^b ± 0.02	0.10 ^{ab} ± 0.00	1.21 ^b ± 0.02	1.81 ^a ± 0.04	0.34 ^a ± 0.11
SGC	0.40 ^c ± 0.00	0.08 ^{bc} ± 0.00	0.70 ^c ± 0.00	1.92 ^a ± 0.00	0.18 ^b ± 0.01
SMB	0.30 ^d ± 0.03	0.06 ^{cd} ± 0.01	0.57 ^d ± 0.06	0.78 ^d ± 0.06	0.15 ^b ± 0.01
SAB	0.21 ^e ± 0.03	0.04 ^{de} ± 0.00	0.38 ^e ± 0.04	1.00 ^{cd} ± 0.11	0.11 ^b ± 0.00
SGB	0.14 ^f ± 0.00	0.02 ^e ± 0.00	0.22 ^f ± 0.00	1.26 ^{bc} ± 0.06	0.07 ^b ± 0.01

The data are mean value \pm standard deviation (SD) of triplicate. Figures with different superscripts in the column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Antinutritional properties

The result of the studied anti-nutrient compounds in eggplant powders is shown in Table 7. The concentrations of saponins, tannins, oxalate, cyanogenic glycosides, and phytate were lower in the blanched samples indicating that the studied anti-nutrient is thermally sensitive. Saponin content in the control samples ranged from 1.08 to 1.40 $\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ whereas in the pretreated samples it ranged from 0.41 to 0.72 $\text{mg}/100\text{g}$. Saponins have been found to be potentially useful for the treatment of hyperglycaemia and carcinogenic effects (Olaleye, 2007). The tanning content recorded in *S. macrocarpon* variety were higher than the content recorded in other varieties. Tannin compounds have been reported to possess some antibacterial, antiviral and antiparasitic effects (Asl and Hossein, 2008). Thus, *S. macrocarpon* variety might have better medicinal properties. Oxalate concentrations were higher in *S. gilo* than in other varieties. It ranged from 0.02 to 0.14 $\text{mg}/100\text{g}$. This was lower than 68.13 - 28.73 $\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ reported by Ossamulu *et al.* (2014). High concentrations of oxalate can bind calcium, magnesium, iron, and zinc making them unavailable, by forming complexes with them (Onwuka, 2018).

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Though higher concentration of oxalate (0.07-0.14 mg/100g) was found in the unblanched samples, however, the values were lower than the lethal dose of 450 mg, which could disrupt metabolic functions (Amaowo, 2000) hence, may not elicit toxic effect when consumed. Cyanogenic glycoside concentrations were low in all the varieties with values ranging from 5.23 to 22.10 µg/100g. Unlike high cyanide concentrations reported in fresh samples of bitter apricot seed, bamboo shoot, cassava, and flaxseed at levels of 9.3 to 330 mg/kg (Dobson, 2010). Blanching reduced the cyanogenic glycoside content in the eggplant powders (9.64 -5.23 mg/100g). Cyanogenic glucosides are heat-labile (Onwuka, 2018). Excessive ingestion of cyanogenic glycosides can be lethal (Clark, 2013). However, the values of cyanogenic glycoside obtained in this work were low and safe for human consumption. Phytate concentrations in the samples ranged from 0.08 to 0.26 µg/100g. Similar to cyanogenic glycosides, the values obtained for phytate were quite low and may not cause any health hazards. Generally, the values obtained in this study revealed the antinutrient compounds in the eggplant were thermal sensitive.

Sensory characteristics

The sensory characteristics of the eggplant powders are presented in Table 8. The blanched samples had higher scores (6.40 - 7.48) for appearance than the unblanched samples (4.72 - 5.92). The taste scores of the blanched eggplant powders were not significantly different from their corresponding control sample. Thus, blanching did not alter the taste of the eggplant powders. The flavour scores were higher for control samples (6.40 -7.28) than blanched samples (5.12 - 6.40). The texture of the blanched samples (4.72 - 5.88) were less preferred to those of the control samples (4.96 - 5.68), indicating that the flavour and texture of the eggplant powders were adversely affected by blanching. Moisture absorption resulting from the blanching operation must have been responsible. The general acceptability values indicated that the pre-treated samples (5.68 – 5.92) were less preferred to the control samples (5.84 – 7.28). The steam blanched samples were observed to have lost the freshness associated with control eggplants.

Table 7: Antinutritional properties of eggplant powders (µg/g).

Sample codes	Saponin	Tannin	Oxalate	Cyanogenic glycoside	Phytate
SMC	1.40 ^a ±0.00	0.18 ^a ±0.01	0.07 ^c ±0.01	22.10 ^a ±0.00	0.26 ^a ±0.01
SAC	1.22 ^b ±0.04	0.16 ^a ±0.01	0.10 ^b ±0.01	19.78 ^b ±0.44	0.22 ^b ±0.00
SGC	1.08 ^c ±0.04	0.13 ^b ±0.01	0.14 ^a ±0.00	16.71 ^c ±0.87	0.17 ^c ±0.00
SMB	0.72 ^d ±0.00	0.09 ^c ±0.01	0.02 ^e ±0.00	9.64 ^d ±0.27	0.13 ^d ±0.01
SAB	0.57 ^e ±0.03	0.05 ^d ±0.00	0.05 ^d ±0.01	7.66 ^e ±0.00	0.11 ^e ±0.01
SGB	0.41 ^f ±0.00	0.03 ^e ±0.01	0.07 ^c ±0.00	5.23 ^f ±0.00	0.08 ^f ±0.01

The data are mean value ± standard deviation (SD) of triplicate samples. Figures with different superscripts in the column are significantly different (p<0.05).

Table 8: Sensory properties of eggplant powders.

Sample codes	Taste	Flavor	Texture	Appearance	General Acceptability
SMC	5.20 ^b ±1.92	7.28 ^a ±1.17	4.96 ^a ±1.54	5.92 ^c ±1.89	5.84 ^b ±1.86
SAC	5.68 ^{ab} ±1.57	6.40 ^a ±1.61	5.32 ^c ±1.89	4.72 ^d ±1.50	7.28 ^a ±1.40
SGC	6.80 ^a ±1.68	6.84 ^a ±1.72	5.68 ^b ±1.73	5.80 ^c ±1.42	7.24 ^a ±1.23
SMB	6.12 ^{ab} ±1.81	6.40 ^a ±1.66	4.72 ^d ±1.65	7.20 ^{ab} ±1.91	5.92 ^b ±1.26
SAB	5.12 ^b ±2.09	5.24 ^b ±2.11	4.60 ^d ±2.00	6.40 ^{bc} ±2.05	5.68 ^b ±1.60
SGB	5.76 ^{ab} ±2.03	5.12 ^b ±1.54	5.88 ^b ±1.48	7.480 ^a ±1.71	5.80 ^b ±1.35

The data are mean value \pm standard deviation (SD) of triplicate. Figures with different superscripts in the column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The present study evaluated the impact of blanching pretreatment on the array of nutrients present in the eggplant fruit. Blanching pretreatment resulted in reduced functional properties with the exception of bulk density. The proximate parameters such as protein and fat were reduced with no impact on the fibre content while the moisture and ash content increased significantly. The mineral content was found to be higher in the blanched eggplant powders in all the varieties. The studied eggplant varieties were not good sources of thiamine, riboflavin, and tocopherol but contained high retinol content and considerable ascorbic acid content. However, blanching pre-treatment resulted in reduced vitamin content in the eggplant powders. Also, blanching resulted in reduced phytochemical and antinutritional components of the eggplant powders. Organoleptically, blanching did not affect the appearance and taste but adversely affected the flavour and texture of the eggplant powders. However, eggplant powders had considerable retention of nutrient, improved mineral composition, and reduced antinutritional compounds. Optimizing the pre-treatment and drying conditions could reduce the loss of valuable nutrients and strengthened the prospects of utilizing eggplant powder to enrich food formulations.

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